

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEARNER PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS: A CASE OF TWENTY SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN LUSAKA DISTRICT

¹Stanley Kalasa, ²Anna Phiri, ³Lufeyo Chitondo

Rockview University, Lusaka Zambia

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to compare the learner's performance in public and private secondary schools in Lusaka district and the study sought to investigate the classroom management styles, classroom activities, teacher-pupil engagement and curriculum implementation in schools. The study employed a mixed paradigm and descriptive survey design that sampled four schools, Head teachers, teachers and learners. Data was obtained from respondents by means of interviews, questionnaires and classroom observation schedules. Frequency, percentages, tables, graphs and pie-charts were used to analyze the quantitative and qualitative data obtained. Data was then analyzed manually in some cases and also, a combination of software MS Access and MS Excel. The findings revealed that classroom management, qualified teachers, positive teacher remunerations, provision of teaching and learning tools, well-established school management team (SMT) control system and sound enrollment system for learners has effects on learners' academic performance and achievement. The study recommended that the school administrators should ensure that teachers' supervisions and monitoring are done and teachers should employ good classroom management skills, teaching strategizing and pupil involvement in classroom activities.

Keywords: Academic, comparative study, learner performance, public school, private school.

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning and academic achievement has been associated with the accomplishments of a particular school in terms of the performance of learners in higher institutions of learning or work places after leaving school (Okoye,2011). Learner output indicates the kind of learning going on in school as the school is particularly and specifically arranged to facilitate effective learning. Unfortunately, the poor condition of school infrastructure, state of furniture and equipment and other relevant resources compromises the quality and volume of learning acquired by children (Igbinedion and Epumepu, 2020).

Several studies by Sociologists, Psychologists and Educationists showed that the type of schools a learner attends has profound influence on his academic achievement. For instance, (Bibby and Peil 2009:57) noted that "children who attended private secondary schools performed better than pupils in public schools." This view is also supported by (Lloyd 2006:123) as he contended further that "the public schools which saw education as good thing, tended to leave the question of educational success or failure in the hands of the public and their parents." This implies that the business of education is not taken with all the seriousness it demands in public schools. This of course is what may be regarded as the general apathy of

the citizenry to government's owned business or property. A situation that has resulted in lackadaisical attitude of government's workers, including teachers in the public schools tend to believe that an intelligent child would succeed automatically at school without any active assistance coming from them. In a study jointly carried out by the Federal Government of Nigeria, UNICEF and UNESCO in 1977 to monitor the learning achievement of primary school pupils throughout the Federation, it was shown that most of the private schools had means in the three areas tested higher than the national means and that of their public counterpart. (Fafunwa 1981) also, observed that access to qualitative instruction, thorough supervision in schools, relevant instructional materials, standard school buildings, less-crowded classrooms, conducive school environment are some of the major school variables influencing pupils' academic attainment.

However, in the study comparing students' academic performance in business studies in public and private Primary School Certificate Examinations in Nigeria conducted by Igbinedion and Epumepu in 2011, it was revealed that there was significant difference in the academic performance in business studies between the public and private schools from 2008 to 2011. Results further showed that the percentage performance trend of public schools were lower than those of the private both males and females. Consequently, many parents and guardians who can afford private education are daily withdrawing their children from public schools to the private fee-paying secondary schools despite its expensive nature even in this hard time. Many of the private schools are growing bigger and faster at the expense of the public ones whose enrolment is daily going down.

1.1 Statement of the problem

There has been a significant comparative differences in the management, performance, and operation of public and private primary schools in terms of management, performance and operations. Academic performance of learners in the Examination Council of Zambia (ECZ) is another factor used to measure deliver of high-quality curriculum (Ejaz, 2019). Classroom management, qualified teachers, positive teacher remunerations, provision of teaching and learning tools, well-established school management team (SMT) control system and sound enrollment system for learners has effects on learners' academic performance and achievement. (Bedi, 2020)

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to compare the learner's performance in public and private secondary schools in Lusaka district by investigating classroom management styles, classroom activities, teacher-pupil engagement and curriculum implementation in schools.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

• *In practical investigations, the study seeks to:*

1. Establish the relationship between school facilities and pupils' performance in public and private primary schools.
2. Explore the relationship between teacher quality and pupils' academic achievement.
3. Find ways of improving the academic performance in primary schools.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the System theory of organization by Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1940s-50s) published in 1968. The systems theory is a theory that says that organizations are composed of many subsystems that aren't necessarily related to one another and yet work together to form the whole and this interconnected components work together to achieve one shared goal (Begum, 2017). Inputs, a transformation mechanism, outputs, feedback, and the environment are all part of the system as two or more people working together to achieve a common objective in an organized manner constitute a school's social network (Jenkins, 2016).

1.5. Significance of the Study

The findings from this study will be useful by all stakeholders in Zambian education system more especially education and school managers and planners by helping them establish how to enhance quality in the education system and to use school resources to play an important role in the teaching and learning process in enhancing pupil performance. The study findings will guide parents, guardians and sponsors in identifying reasons how they should identify better schools for quality

education instead of any other motive to enroll their children in schools. Besides, to the Ministry of education and policy makers; the study findings will provide information on the inequality in education between the rich and the poor and they will also reveal to them that this inequality is not only in types of school attended but quality of output from these schools to enhance national development.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Teaching and learner development

The overall objective in every teaching-learning interaction as usually required is to bring about harmonious development of the individual and acquisition of the desired knowledge, values and skills to enable him/her function in a particular way. The process of teaching needs to be supervised for effective teaching-learning process. The syllabus and curriculum system must be given special care and consideration so as to achieve the desired objectives. Thus, when curriculum system is ensured in every school, there will be positive developments that will bring permanent change in the behavior of the learner signifying that learning has taken place (Fafunwa, 2018).

However, schools in Zambia differ in the way they teach learners values, norms and skills, while others impart skills in formal way, through organized system, that is a well-recognized system approved by the ministry of education. Others prefer more traditional ways in inculcating such desired values, notwithstanding the particular society in which learning takes place, and methodology used, a number of variables interact together to bring about a stable and permanent change in behavior. Consequently, besides the two important variables mentioned in teaching-learning process, the environment in which learning takes place has to be conducive for learning. In formal learning, schools are not just a place to learn, to read and write but also receive complete education. Therefore, schools have to provide suitable environment for effective and proper development of the learner so as to acquire the desired skills, but where the school environment is deficient or lacking in the materials required for effective learning as in the case of most if not all public schools, the designed objectives could not be achieved (Lloyd, 2006). However, education is a very costly project for nations and individual families. Therefore, it is very crucial to understand the factors affecting its provisions and the performance of learners. The majority of studies on student performance have related student performance to various aspects of education, such as school quality, teaching quality, teacher remuneration, class size, and Learners' characteristics (Kingdon and Teal, 2002).

2.2 Teacher Remuneration

Remuneration refers to payment or compensation received for services or employment. This includes the base salary and any bonuses or other economic benefits that an employee or executive receives during employment, (Investopedia, 2010). Thus, teacher remuneration refers to the total compensation received by a teacher, which includes not only the base salary but options, bonuses, expense accounts and other forms of compensation. A study on schools in India investigated the relationship between performance-related pay and student achievement (Kingdon & Teal, 2002), addressing the important issue of endogeneity in the relationship between pay and achievement. They found strong evidence that performance-related pay in the private sector affects student achievement, but no evidence of a similar cause-effect relationship.

In Rwandan education system, private schools' teachers are better paid than in public schools. This difference in payment is very important at primary school level where a private secondary school teacher earns up to three times the salary of a public primary school teacher. The fact that a teacher is well paid plays an important role on his or her work performance and on his/her pupils' performance as well. Even though the salary may not be the main motivator of teachers, it plays a very important role in this issue (Ibid).

Regarding the importance of teachers in general, (Bibby and Peil 2009) argue that teachers are the most important influence on student progress, even more important than socioeconomic status and school location. Furthermore, Bibby and Peil conclude that measures of teacher preparation and certification are by far the strongest correlates of student achievement in reading and mathematics.

2.3 Teacher Quality

Teachers are central to any consideration of schools, and a majority of education policy discussions focus directly or indirectly on the role of teachers. There is a prima facie case for the concentration on teachers, because they are the largest single budgetary element in schools (World Bank, 2003). Moreover, parents, teachers, and administrators emphasize

repeatedly the fundamental role that teachers play in the determination of school quality. Yet there remains little consensus among researchers on the characteristics of a good teacher, let alone on the importance of teachers in comparison to other determinants of academic performance. Teacher quality is the concept that embodies what the teacher does and they can do in terms of their assigned roles in the school. Related to the concept of teacher quality is teaching quality and it has been observed that one way of determining the quality of teaching in schools is by looking at the intermediate outcome of student performance. There are several ways to evaluate a student's quality attributable to formal education, but the most tractable indicator is how he or she performs in tests.

2.4 Teachers' Professional Qualifications and experience

Teacher quality involves the level of qualification and research on the value of a teacher's advanced degree is mixed: some studies show that while additional teacher education has a positive correlation with student achievement in some cases, others find that it negatively affects achievement. In this regard, Okoye (2011) found that a teacher's advanced degree is not generally associated with increased student learning from the eighth to the tenth grade, but having an advanced degree in math and science for math and science teachers appears to influence students' achievement. The same results were not found to be true for teachers of English or history. In the same way, Lloyd (2006) suggests that the findings of other studies about the impact on student achievement of teachers' advanced degrees are inconclusive because they considered only the level of the degree and not the subject of the degree, which may affect student achievement in different ways than the degree level. Nevertheless, results from all the studies seem to imply that there is not a positive correlation between teachers having advanced degrees in subjects other than those they teach and student achievement.

There is a wide range of findings on the relationship between years of teaching experience and student outcomes. Alderman et al. (2001) found that fewer than half of the 109 previous studies on the estimated effects of teacher experience showed that experience had any statistically significant effect on student achievement; of those, 33 studies found that additional years of experience had a significant positive effect, but seven found that more experience actually had a negative impact on student achievement. Other studies show a stronger positive relationship between teacher experience and student outcomes in some, but not all, cases they reviewed.

2.5 School and Class Sizes

About class size, a comparative study of public schools among US states found that in Tennessee, smaller class sizes contribute positively to student learning, particularly in fields like elementary reading (Suryadarma et al., 2006). In another assessment, Suryadarma et al. further used regression-discontinuity design and find that reducing class size increases fourth- and fifth-grade test scores in Israeli public schools. For the case of Rwandan schools, public primary schools are very crowded (especially because of EFA principles) at an extent of 70 pupils and beyond per class while in private primary schools, a big class doesn't host more than 35 pupils. This can be a positive factor of good pupils' performance in private schools in that teacher can individualize his or her teaching very easily if the class is not too big. Similarly, Tariq et al. (2012) separate their sample of South African data into races, notably Blacks and Whites, and look at the impact of pupil-teacher ratio on education attainment, enrolment, and numerical and literacy test scores. Especially for the test score results among Blacks, they find that when school facilities and education attainment are included as controls, a higher pupil-teacher ratio has a negative effect on mathematics score but a positive and insignificant effect on literacy. If higher pupil-teacher ratio has a negative effect on math score it is because math asks a great concentration and, in most cases, an individualization of teaching. Being so, all teaching subjects that need a great concentration like geography, physics, chemistry etc. are likely to be negatively influenced by a high pupil-teacher ratio.

2.6 Availability and Adequacy of Educational Resources

On the availability and adequacy of school resources, it is obvious that in Rwanda as in any other third world country, private schools are more favored than public ones. Considering the relationship between educational resources and students' academic performance, teacher's qualification and adequate facilities may be determinants of assessing academic performance of students. Hence, the availability or non-availability of facilities and their adequacy in schools have an effect on the academic performance of pupils in schools (Ejaz et al., 2012). This is in agreement with some educationalists who believe that teaching materials facilitate teaching and learning activities, which result in effective teaching and improve academic performance. The school is an essentially human organization; because it has human operatives, clients and

products, hence students' performance has positive relationship with the quality of teachers. The importance of adequate staffing of a school is clearly demonstrated by the way parents continue to drift from one school to another in search of school with better qualified teachers. For efficient educational management, facilities help the school to determine the number of pupils to be accommodated, number of teachers and non-teaching personnel to be employed and the cost determination for the efficient management of the system.

The school climate is determined by the resources, especially class rooms under which the teachers and pupils operate which influences attitude in teaching and learning. Un-conducive classroom creates stress on teachers and pupils resulting in negative attitude toward school and learning by pupils. Facilities below approved standard could also lead to reduction in quality of teaching and learning in schools causing poor pupils' academic performance. The school environment affects academic achievement of pupils. Facilities such as, desks, seats, chalkboard, teaching aids, and cupboard are ingredients for effective teaching and learning. A good education policy or programmed to guarantee quality outputs, it must be serviced optimally with appropriate trained and motivated teaching staff, adequately supplied with necessary facilities and equipment (U.S Department of Education, 2012). In other words, a good school must have adequate resources which may be divided into three categories: Financial resources, human resources and physical (material) resources. The human resources are teachers and the non-teaching staff, and physical resources mean facilities including classrooms, desks, toilets, offices, books and teaching aids; all these resources cannot be acquired without financial resources.

Because public schools are required to admit all students, the students attending them paint a picture of the community they come from. As such, there is often a diverse mixture of backgrounds present in public schools. Private schools tend to be more homogenous due to the admission and selection process and the type of student that will apply to take part in a private school based on its reputation (Begum and Sadrudin, 2013). One common reason for sending a child to private school is the private school is the smaller class sizes. Private schools can afford to keep class sizes small, thus providing more frequent interaction and attention on the teacher-student level which is a desirable feature. When the law says that all children have the right to be educated, this includes students with special needs. Public schools offer education programs for those who are physically or mentally handicapped in some fashion and provide teachers who are qualified to work with these needs. As mentioned before, private schools can admit or deny an applicant based on their own criteria, and this includes special educational needs. Although there are some private schools intended solely for those with these needs, many private schools do not accept special education cases.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The research design was descriptive survey with both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection in order to attain the comprehensive results (Creswell 2008)). Qualitative methods was appropriate to this investigation as it produced detailed data from a small group of participants, while exploring feelings, impressions and judgments. On the other hand, quantitative method made the use of questionnaires, surveys and experiment to gather data that is revised and tabulated in numbers, which allows the data to be characterized by use of statistical analysis Martyn, (2008).

3.2 Research sites

The study was carried out in the twenty (20) selected secondary schools-10 public (Kabulonga boys, Kabulonga Girls, Twin Palm, Nyumba Yanga, Matero, Roma, Kamwala, Munali Boys, Munali Girls and Kanda Square) and 10 private (St. Mary's, Lake Road, Kabulonga, Kings Highway, Convent, Masabo, Child, Licef, Indian and American) of Lusaka district in Lusaka Province.

3.3 Population, Sample and Sampling procedure

The population for the study was purposefully drawn from the twenty secondary schools- ten- public and ten private. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select Head teachers (20), snowball sampling procedure was used to select parents (200) while the simple random sampling procedure was used to select the teachers (80) and learners (200), (Bickel, 2007). The sample size comprised of 500 respondents. Also, the primary data was complimented by the secondary data which was derived from government policy documents, ministerial reports and relevant literature on distance to school, learner absenteeism and poverty.

In the sampling of institutions, the study adopted the stratified cluster random sampling technique. Sampling was done on the basis of public and private school and zone by zone. Schools were clustered by zones. Six zones were purposively selected based on the basis of school concentration. The sampling was done at three levels: Sampling zones and schools-level 1, Sampling Head teachers, teachers and parents-level 2, Sampling learners -level 3.

3.4 Data Analysis

In this research, data was analysed qualitatively as in-depth interviews, questionnaires and observation schedules were used as data collection instruments. Thematic approach was used, where data analysis started with the categorization of themes from the structured interviews, questionnaires and observation schedules Kombo and Tromp (2006). Charts and graphs were used to analyse data. The data gathered was analysed according to the themes of the study and per the order of the research objectives. Data generated from the interview guide was analysed manually and also, a combination of software MS Access, SPSS and MS Excel was used to analyse data. Analysis was mainly descriptive, that is, mean, median, mode, range, and standard deviation. Related statistics were applied where possible. Statistical testing took the form of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), correlation and regression both simple and multiple, (Buetow, 2010:123-125).

3.5 Ethical Issues

The researcher avoided pressuring respondents to take part in the research. Alternatively, permission consents, assents were obtained from respondents involved in the research and the research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents. In this research, the researcher was fully conscious of the need to abide by the ethical rule of respecting the privacy of individuals taking part in the research (Miles and Huberman 2014). In the same way, all the respondents of the research were to remain unidentified to the public as all their valuable views, opinions and perceptions were only known by the researcher for use only in the research and participant's identities will forever remain hidden.

The Researcher got permission from the District Education Board Secretary to interview Head teachers while permission was got from the Head teachers to interview teachers, learners and parents. The names of respondents would remain anonymous for the sake of confidentiality, Bryman (2001) and Diener and Crandall (2008). However, the identity of respondents was concealed in the thesis but for identification in the thesis, the learners were allocated numbers 1 to 100, the parents were allocated ordinal numbers 1st to 100th, the teachers were allocated names of 80 private primary schools in Lusaka while the Head teachers were allocated letters A to T.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Availability and suitability of teaching and learning facilities

According to study results, schools used the following facilities to teach: the most available were classroom space (25%), furniture (20%) and ICT equipment (15%) while least used or available resources were toilets (4%) then water and sports facilities and equipment (3%), laboratories, science laboratories and library (10%). Study results also indicated that 79% of the schools had adequate teaching and learning materials against 21% who were not able to show examples of the materials they had in stock. The other facilities were teachers' preparation rooms at 3%, departmental stock rooms at 2% and the least were departmental and class libraries at 1.5% each. This is illustrated in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Distribution of teaching and learning facilities

Teaching and learning facilities	Actual	Percentage	
		Yes	No
Classroom space	125	25.0	75.0
Furniture	100	20.0	80.0
ICT equipment	75	15.0	85.0
Laboratories	50	10.0	60.0
Laboratory equipment	50	10.0	60.0
Toilets	20	4.0	96.0
Library	15	10.0	90.0
Water	10	3.0	97.0
Sports equipment	10	3.0	97.0

Teaching and learning facilities are essential to a teacher in order for effective teaching as the facilities motivate the teacher to put in his or her best and this is in line with literature as (Strickland and Riley-Ayers, 2006) indicates that teaching and learning facilities enhance effective teaching and learning. From the study, most of the sampled schools did not have adequate and appropriate teaching and learning facilities for learner instruction as well as to support quality teaching and education and the absence of adequate and appropriate teaching and learning facilities deprived learners the opportunity to learn effectively. According to (MESVTEE 2013:3)“The success of any teaching programme also depends on the availability of suitable facilities to sustain and reinforce acquisition of skills”.

4.2 Suitability of teaching methods and techniques used in schools

Interactive teaching methods and techniques are important in teaching and the teacher should vary the methods and techniques. Also, teaching methods and techniques need to place greater emphasis on self-initiated and self-sustained learning because teaching methods and techniques used in teaching learners are critical to the success of teaching programmes.

Regarding teaching methods, survey results as illustrated in Table 2 below, showed that teachers scored highly on teacher-centred method (78.4%), followed by learner-centred method at 73.6%, small group instruction method (69.7%), inquiry based learning at 53.6% and the least used method was the project based learning approach at 49.6%.

Table 2: Distribution of methods used when teaching English language

Teaching method	Percentage	
	Yes	No
Teacher-centred	78.4%	21.6%
Learner-centred	73.6%	26.4%
Small group instruction	69.7%	30.3%
Inquiry-based learning	53.6%	46.4%
Project-based learning	49.6%	50.4%

On frequency of teaching, the results showed that the most common frequency of teaching using the five major teaching methods and strategies in sampled schools was daily (69.2%) and weekly (30.8%) while the frequency for specifically teaching English, Mathematics and Science was 53% daily and 47% weekly. The most common method used to teach all the subjects in sampled schools was answering questions (37.1%), followed by discussions (19.4%), making connections as a group or pair (18.6%), building relationship (11.3%), other (7.0%) and lastly cooperative learning (5.6%).

Literature reviews that techniques carry out a method that is consistent with an approach whereas, an approach on the other hand, is a set of correlative assumptions dealing with the nature of language teaching and learning. (National Reading Panel, 2000). According to (MOE, 1996:27) “teaching methodologies need to place greater emphasis on self-initiated and self-sustained learning.” Other studies (MESVTEE, 2013) advised that the teacher should use methods that encourage learners to reflect, think and do rather than reproduce from rote learning.

The common methods teachers used in teaching as reviewed by findings from this study were teacher-centred, learner-centred, small group instruction, inquiry based learning and project based learning. Above all, children learn more effectively if a teacher uses a variety of teaching methods and according to (Quist 2000:78): “before you choose a particular teaching method think about the knowledge and skills of your pupils, their ability and the kind of experience they can bring to the lessons.” Teaching methods and techniques should be used according to learners’ experience and must vary if effective teaching and learning has to be encouraged especially in all the subjects at Junior secondary level.

4.3 Learner Assessment

(Paris and Paris 2003:57), literature indicated that, “systematic assessments lead to improved performance.” In this study, results showed that teachers mostly assessed learners by asking questions as illustrated in Table 3 below. Further analysis showed that there was a tilt towards more informed classroom-based assessment practices than the formalized and more verifiable school- based assessment techniques. As highlighted in Table 3, 83.3% of the teachers assessed by asking questions, 66.7% assessed by monitoring learners as they work, 50.0% assessed by observing, 33.3% assessed by listening to individual learners read or do an activity while only 16.7% and 16.7% of observed teachers assessed learners by using assessment tool and giving quiz respectively. On assessment, teacher Mumana from Roma secondary school said, “at our school, Iam allowed to come up with my own type of assessment and what the Head teacher is interested in are results and

not the way I conduct assessment,” while teacher Mandevu from Kabulonga Junior secondary school said, “at our school we don’t sit as a group to prepare assessment questions and therefore, each teacher prepares whatever he or she feels fits the learners.”

Table 3: Comparison of most and least commonly used assessment technique

Type of technique	Actual	percentage
Asking questions	5	83%
Monitoring learners	4	66.70%
Observing learners	3	50%
Listening to learners read	2	33.30%
Using assessment tool	1	16.70%
Quiz	1	16.70%

Overall Learner Assessment results reviewed that achievement skills were low on the sub-tasks assessed among Grade 9 learners in the targeted schools. Very few learners in the sample could for example read with enough fluency to allow for real comprehension. The study also revealed learners who were unable to answer given questions correctly (53.5%). Literature, showed that learners were to be fast in completing given tasks or answering quiz questions if they were to succeed in their future education development (Chiappe et al, 2002). It should be noted that learners’ inability to read was therefore, a reflection on teachers’ poor pedagogical practices

4.4 Factors to enhance learner performance

In this study, results showed that there are various factors that enhance learner performance were qualified teachers (100%), good pay and incentives (98%), availability of resources (5%), good control systems (89%) and good enrolment system (59%) as illustrated in Table 4 below. Further analysis showed that there was need for adequate staff, local teacher monitoring, teacher collaboration, teacher freedom and man other factors.

Table 4: Factors to enhance learner performance

Factors	Total respondents	Yes %	No %
• Qualified teachers	300	100	0
• Good pay and incentive	300	98	02
• Availability of resources	300	56	44
• Good control system	300	89	11
• Good enrollment system	300	59	41

Study findings showed teacher remuneration were essential and this refers to the total compensation received by a teacher, which includes not only the base salary but options, bonuses, expense accounts and other forms of compensation (Kingdon and Teal, 2002), They found strong evidence that performance-related pay in the private sector affects student achievement, but no evidence of a similar cause-effect relationship. About class size, smaller class sizes contribute positively to student learning, particularly in fields like elementary reading (Suryadarma et al., 2006) and that reducing class size increases grade test scores in schools.

On the availability and adequacy of school resources and considering the relationship between educational resources and students' academic performance, teacher's qualification and adequate facilities may be determinants of assessing academic performance of students. Hence, the availability or non-availability of facilities and their adequacy in schools have an effect on the academic performance of pupils in schools (Ejaz et al., 2012). This is in agreement with some educationalists who believe that teaching materials facilitate teaching and learning activities, which result in effective teaching and improve academic performance.

4.5 Teacher’s motivation and Academic Performance.

It is said that motivation is a psychological force that guides humans to achieve a predetermined objective. "People's concerns about their personal lives are full of motivational problems" (Kispál-Vitai, 2016). Since teachers are not the exception and can be motivated or de-motivated by challenges and situations around them, a teacher's action is framed by the degree of motivation that he owns. (Bieg et al. 2011:88) says that “the tutor's positive conduct is very critical for the quality of the training they get for the learners.” Intrinsic motivation influences the performance of teachers in management

and the key predictor of the academic success of the teachers was the intrinsic motivational factors and the elements that motivated teachers were their co-workers as a family, feeling of calling, love of children, dedication to society, and service to others (Casey, 2016).

5. CONCLUSION

In secondary schools, teachers' pedagogical practices, use of teaching and learning materials, innovativeness and greater devotion of greater portion of teaching learners are essential in learner instructions. Findings from the study showed that overall, there were factors that were essential to enhance teacher performance as these foster educational problems and how they affect learner's output. Lack of teacher motivation and poor school environment culminate into explicit unpreparedness and mastery of the subject caused problems to teachers during class sessions. There were inadequate and inappropriate teaching and learning materials, inappropriate teaching methods and inadequate internal and external teacher monitoring.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Ministry of education should deploy adequate and qualified teachers to secondary schools so as to reduce on class sizes.
2. Continuing Professional Development (CPD) is needed in specific instructional strategies and methods focused on components of the curriculum,
3. Administrators should encourage team work in the production of teaching and learning materials at school and zone levels as well as hold teaching and learning aids exhibitions at these levels so as to inculcate the spirit of innovativeness in teachers
4. Ministry of education should ensure that teachers are motivated in terms of. good pay and incentives
5. Schools should focus on approved and workable teaching methods, techniques and approaches to the teaching of subjects across the curriculum,
6. School Head teachers should ensure that all the teachers are internally monitored by all the school administrators.
7. The Ministry of education must strengthen the schools by devolving some of the responsibilities to the community and the community, the School Management Committee, and any government agency can all work together to improve the schools.
8. The public school should be run as a system where every part of the system has their roles to fulfill and there is a management policy which is responsible to get the best out of the parts of the system.

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AUTHOR' BIOGRAPHY

Stanley Kalasa specializes in Special Education and is currently lecturing at Rockview University in the Department of Special Education

Anna Phiri specializes in Textile Design and Technology and is currently lecturing at Rockview University in the Department of Home Economics

Lufeyo Chitondo specializes in Language Education and is currently lecturing at Rockview University in the Department of Literature and Languages.